

Integrated pest management—weeds

Evaluation of herbicides for transplanted rice (TPR) in Kerala, India

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We evaluated 16 weed control treatments using six preemergence herbicides and hand weeding during kharif (monsoon, Jun-Oct) 1989 and rabi (wet season, Nov-Mar) 1989–90 for chemical weed control in TPR.

The field experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. MO-6 rice (115 d) was transplanted at 15- × 15-cm spacing in a silty clay lowland. Urea, Mussoorie rock phosphate, and muriate of potash were applied at 90-20-38 kg NPK/ha: N and K were applied in two equal splits at planting and 30 d after transplanting (DT), and P was applied fully as basal.

Herbicides were applied on a thin film of water 3 or 7 DT as per treatment. Weeds were hand-removed at fortnightly intervals until 45 DT in weed-free check (WFC) and at 20 and 40 DT in hand weeding twice (HWT).

Weeds at 55 DT were 22% grasses, 44% sedges, and 34% broadleaf weeds. Important species were *Echinochloa colona*, *E. crus-galli*, *Tragus* sp., *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Cyperus iria*, *C. difformis*, *C. halpan*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Schoenoplectus* spp., *Juncus* spp., *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Limnocharis flava*, *Ludwigia perennis*, *L. adscendens*, *Marsilea quadrifolia*, *Sphenoclea zeylmica*, *Lobelia alsinoides*, and *Lindernia rotundifolia*.

All herbicides except thiobencarb significantly reduced weed growth compared with the unweeded control and were statistically comparable to the WFC and HWT treatments (see table). Treatments significantly affected rice yields, but there was no significant interaction between seasons and treatments.

Pyrazosulfuron-ethyl 0.005 and 0.01 kg 7 DT and pretilachlor 1.25 kg

Effect of weed control treatments on TPR. Kerala, India, 1989-90.

Treatment	Dose ^a (kg ai/ha)	Time (DT)	Weed dry wt (g/m ²)	Mean rice yields (t/ha)		Gross return (\$/ha)	Benefit of weed control (\$/ha)	cost of weed control (\$/ha)	Marginal benefit-cost ratio
				Grain	Straw				
Pyrazosulfuron-ethyl	0.005	3	106.1	3.0	4.3	618	184	—	—
Pyrdzosulfuron-ethyl	0.005	7	70.9	3.3	4.7	677	243	—	—
Pyrazosulfuron-ethyl	0.01	3	79.8	3.1	4.6	645	211	—	—
Pyrazosulfuron-ethyl	0.01	7	81.8	3.3	4.7	682	248	—	—
Pretilachlor	0.75	3	53.4	3.1	4.4	640	206	11.8	17.5
Pretilachlor	0.75	7	84.1	3.0	4.2	621	187	11.8	15.8
Pretilachlor	1.25	3	75.0	3.3	4.7	676	242	18.3	13.2
Pretilachlor	1.25	7	110.7	3.2	5.0	658	224	18.3	12.2
Anilophos	0.40	7	85.7	3.2	4.5	652	218	13.6	16.0
Anilophos	0.60	7	82.0	3.1	4.6	648	214	19.4	11.0
Oxadiazon	0.40	7	79.2	3.1	4.4	633	199	15.6	12.8
Tridiphane	0.40	7	101.6	2.8	4.1	583	149	25.9	5.8
Thiobencarb	1.00	7	121.4	2.9	4.4	595	161	24.0	6.7
Weed-free check	—	—	65.6	3.5	4.8	730	296	92.4	3.2
Hand weeding twice	—	—	74.7	3.4	4.8	693	259	64.6	4.0
Unweeded control	—	—	175.8	2.1	2.9	434	—	—	—
LSD (0.05)	—	—	60.3	0.3	0.6	—	—	—	—

^aai = active ingredient. Cost of pyrazosulfuron-ethyl 10 WP not available; pretilachlor 50 EC, \$6.5/liter; anilophos 30 EC, \$8.7/liter; oxadiazon 25 EC, \$8.5/liter; tridiphane 48 EC, \$28.67/11ter; thiobencarb 10 G, \$2.2/kg; hand weeding, \$1.42/person per d; rice grain, \$200/t; straw, \$5/t.

3 DT had grain yields and gross returns equal to that of the WFC. Herbicide treatments pretilachlor (0.75 kg) and

anilophos (6.4 kg ai/ha) were more economic than hand weeding according to marginal benefit-cost ratio. □

Evaluation of Bromadiolone in irrigated ricefields

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We studied a single-dose anticoagulant rodenticide to establish the suitable

period for poison baiting.

Bandicota bengalensis, *Millardia meltada*, and *Mus booduga* considerably damage rice fields of Tanjore District, Tamil Nadu. Seven plots (0.5 km²) were treated with bromadiolone 0.005% wax cakes (burrow baiting) at 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, and 70 d after transplanting (DT).

Reference plots were also maintained.

Live burrows and percent successful control of rodents by using bromadiolone 0.005% wax cake during various rice growth stages.

Treatment (d after transplanting)	Tiller damage (%)	Live burrows ^a (no./ha)											
		<i>B. bengalensis</i>			<i>M. meltada</i>			<i>M. booduga</i>			Total		
		I (no.)	II (no.)	Control (%)	I (no.)	II (no.)	Control (%)	I (no.)	II (no.)	Control (%)	I (no.)	II (no.)	Control (%)
20	2.1	12.0	0.8	93.3	2.4	0.8	66.7	3.2	0.8	75.0	17.6	2.4	86.4
30	4.4	13.6	0.8	94.1	4.8	1.6	66.7	7.2	1.6	77.8	25.6	4.0	84.4
40	7.0	18.4	1.6	91.3	4.0	0.8	80.0	10.4	3.2	69.2	31.2	5.6	87.2
50	2.5	16.8	4.0	81.0	8.0	0.8	90.0	12.0	4.0	66.7	36.8	8.8	78.3
60	3.4	20.0	4.0	80.0	11.2	4.8	57.1	13.6	4.8	64.7	44.8	13.6	69.6
70	5.2	24.0	11.2	53.3	9.6	4.0	58.3	16.8	5.0	76.2	50.4	19.2	61.9
Reference plot (mean)	9.4	20.0			8.8			7.2			36.0		

^aI = pretreatment, II = posttreatment.

We used the live burrow count method to estimate rodent activity.

Burrows were at a minimum during the early rice growth stages; by maturity the number was remarkably higher. About 9.4% of the tillers were damaged in the reference fields. Treatment at the

early rice cultivation stages (20, 30, and 40 DT) reduced live burrows by 84.4-87.2%. Later treatment (50, 60, and 70 DT) reduced tiller damage by 96.6-97.9% (see table).

Immigrants may have caused the large tiller cut damage observed in plots at 40

DT (7.0%) and 70 DT (5.2%). Control may be less successful as rice matures because the rodents consume more of the grain and less of the poison baits.

Bromadiolone 0.005% wax cake should be used during the early rice growth stages for greatest effectiveness. □

ANNOUNCEMENTS

Asian Rice Farming Systems Working Group recommendations

The Asian Rice Farming Systems Working Group met in Beijing, China, 30 Sep-4 Oct 1991. Representatives of member countries presented progress reports and discussed future directions.

The Working Group stressed the need for stronger emphasis on

- Cost effectiveness in farming systems approach
- Linkages among governments, research institutions, and the private sector
- Integration of crop processing, nutrition, and marketing into the current thrust of increased crop production approach
- Farmer participatory research
- Sustainability of farming systems. □

New IRRI publications

A logical framework for planning agricultural research programs, by Schubert et al

Biofertilizer germplasm collections at IRRI

New IRRN section begins in June

News about research collaboration will be a new section in the IRRN beginning in June. The objective is timely communication to rice scientists of news about collaborative activities from consortia, networks, collaborating groups, etc.

The section will include general news and current update items (new projects, work plans, new heads, etc.) about consortia, networks, country and regional projects, conference

New publications

Rainfed rice production in the Philippines: a combined agronomic/ economic study of Antique Province.

K. M. Menz, ed. Published by the Australian Centre for International Agricultural Research. For more information contact ACIAR, Philippine Liaison Office, P.O. Box 1274 MCC, Makati, Philippines. Fax: 8173603.

The 1992 Information Please Environmental Almanac. A. Hammond, ed. An almanac of local, national, and international environmental facts. 606 pages. For more information contact WRI

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A calendar of conferences, symposia, workshops, training courses, meetings, IRRI activities, etc. will also be added. □

Publications, P.O. Box 4852, Hampden Station, Baltimore MD21211. Telephone: 410-516-6963.

Rice Biotechnology. G. S. Khush and G. H. Toenniessen, eds. An authoritative review of the progress and prospects for applying biotechnology to rice improvement. Published by CABI and IRRI. Send requests from highly developed countries to CABI, Wallingford, Oxon OX10 8DE, UK. Fax: (0491) 33508. Send requests from less developed countries to IRRI, Box 933, Manila 1099, Philippines. □

ERRATUM

Virulence of a new biotype of brown planthopper (BPH) in Mekong Delta, by Luong Minh Chau. In column 2 of the table on page 14, MTL 85 should read MTL 58.